

Peach Bottom 2 Turbine Trip 2 Calculation with Nodal Transient Code SIMULATE5-K

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ABSTRACT

SIMULATE5-K is a transient nodal code which employs advanced neutronics and core thermal-hydraulic solvers, and has models implemented for the BWR vessel and steam lines. This paper presents the validation of SIMULATE5-K for a turbine trip experiment performed in Peach Bottom 2 plant. The results show a good agreement with the measured power peak and the LPRM detectors. The steam dome pressure is underpredicted by SIMULATE5-K by about 50 kPa. The more extreme transient scenario defined in the NEA benchmark specification, combining the turbine trip with bypass valve opening failure and no scram, was additionally calculated with SIMULATE5-K, and the results show good agreement with other published results.

Keywords: Turbine trip, Peach Bottom, SIMULATE5-K, SIMULATE5, transient

1. INTRODUCTION

SIMULATE5-K (S5K) is a nodal transient analysis code developed at Studsvik [1]. The accuracy of neutronic and core thermal hydraulic modules was previously tested by modeling the TWIGL, LMW, LRA BWR, NEACRP and URW benchmarks [1,2], or the SPERT-III and Frigg experiments [3,4]. In this paper, the vessel and steam line models implemented in S5K are tested for a turbine trip experiment.

The S5K models the BWR vessel components (upper plenum, standpipes, steam separators, steam dome, upper and lower downcomer, recirculation loops, lower plenum, core) as discretized 1D components, except for the steam dome and the upper downcomer, which are modeled as single nodes. The effect of the turbine and the steam line can be explicitly modeled by the steam line model. The effect of the feedwater system can be also considered. The model can be used for operational transients and stability analysis.

The Peach Bottom 2 plant performed series of turbine trip (TT) measurements at the end of cycle 2 (in 1977) and made the data available for validation of transient codes [5]. The operating data of the first cycles until the TT tests are also available. In this paper, the nodal steady state code SIMULATE5 was used to simulate the cycle depletion until the start of the transient. The lattice code CASMO5 was used to generate the nuclear data for both SIMULATE5 and S5K. The code, vessel, and the transient scenario were modeled using the EPRI report and the NEA benchmark specification [6].

2. SIMULATE5-K METHODOLOGY

The neutronics and core thermal hydraulic methods of S5K are mostly consistent with the methods of the steady state code SIMULATE5 [7]. The neutronics module solves the time-dependent multi-group diffusion equation and employs the analytical nodal method. The nodal data are rehomogenized based on 2D radial and 1D axial finer subnode solutions.

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The core thermal-hydraulic nodalization corresponds to the neutronic nodes. The five-equation model is implemented, solving the vapor and liquid mass conservation, the vapor and liquid energy conservation, and the mixture momentum balance equations for each axial subnode of a channel.

The BWR vessel module is also based on the five-equation model, like the core channel hydraulics. The vessel is composed of components depicted in Figure 1. The following assumptions are made in modeling the BWR vessel:

1. Upper plenum, standpipes and steam separators are modeled at saturated or subcooled conditions. Water/steam properties are evaluated at the local pressure and enthalpy conditions.
2. Core channel properties are evaluated at the local pressure and enthalpy conditions.
3. A single value of slip is used for the upper plenum, standpipes, and steam separators.
4. The upper downcomer is modeled as a single node at saturated or subcooled conditions. Water/steam properties are evaluated at the steam dome pressure.
5. Lower downcomer, recirculation loops and lower plenum are modeled at saturated or subcooled conditions. Water/steam properties are evaluated at the local pressure and enthalpy conditions.
6. There is a perfect mixing of the feedwater flow and the recirculation flow at the interface upper downcomer – lower downcomer.

Figure 1. BWR Vessel Components scheme as implemented in S5K.

The specific flow conditions are calculated by considering recirculation pump, jet pump, and steam separators models. The recirculation pumps drive the recirculation flow through the recirculation loops into the jet pumps or drive the core flow in a plant with internal pumps. The pump pressure rise is calculated as a function of the volumetric flow rate and speed using homologous pump curves. The pump speed may be given as a function of time or can be computed using the motor, hydraulic and friction torques. The jet pump model calculates the pump head in the internal jet pumps. All the jet

pumps in one recirculation loop are lumped together. The jet pump model consists of a mixing region in which the drive flow is mixed with the suction flow and one recirculation (drive) loop containing the recirculation pump. The steam separator model considers the following effects: flow inertia in the separators, pressure losses in the separators, and carry under flow.

The steam line model simulates the acoustic effects in the steam line due to sudden valve closures or openings, leading to pressure waves traveling back and forth in the steam line. Strong pressure pulses in the steam line will in turn induce pressure pulses in the steam dome and core, thus causing a void collapse in the core and a sudden increase in reactivity. The steam line module solves single-phase equations for conservation of mass, momentum, and energy.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Steady State

The steady state nodal code SIMULATE5 was used to deplete the first two fuel cycles, using the operating history data with 24 datasets for the first cycle and 13 datasets for the second cycle. The simulated power and flow conditions are depicted in Figures 2-3. These data are typically used by the NEA benchmark participants; the real operating history was however more complicated especially in the first cycle with almost 20 outages [5]. During one of the outages, some of holes in the core support plate were plugged, which has also significant impact on the bypass flow.

The nuclear data were generated with the lattice code CASMO5 and the SIMULATE5 calculations were run in 4 energy groups. During the first cycle, the multiplication factor is underpredicted by SIMULATE5, likely due to the more complicated operating history. During the second cycle with more stable power, the predicted eigenvalue is closer to 1. The accuracy of the depletion is sufficient to provide the starting point for the transient. The xenon transient prior the turbine trip was not simulated, the equilibrium xenon distribution corresponding to the TT initial power was used. The axial power and xenon profile at the beginning of the TT are in good agreement with the benchmark specification (Figure 4).

Figure 2. Cycle 1 depletion.

Figure 3. Cycle 2 depletion.

Figure 4. Axial power and xenon distribution at the initial point of the transient.

3.2. Turbine Trip 2

The turbine trip 2 test was performed at the end of cycle 2, with initial power at about 60% of nominal power. The dome pressure starts to rise approximately 0.4 s after the turbine valve closure. This initial response is well predicted by S5K, the maximum calculated pressure is however lower than the measured one by approximately 50 kPa (Figure 5). It should be noted here that the total error of the pressure measurement in the range of 1000 psi (6900 kPa) was calculated as 0.5% [8].

The total power and the LPRM (Local Power Range Monitor) detector response calculated by S5K are normalized to match the measured values at the beginning of the transient. The power peak predicted

by S5K is in very good agreement with the measured values. The PRM detector measurements in 4 axial levels are shown in Figure 6. S5K predicts the peak values within 10%.

Figure 5. Relative power and dome pressure during TT2.

Figure 6. LPRM in 4 axial levels during TT2.

3.3. Extreme Scenarios

The NEA benchmark specification defines additional, more severe scenarios for code-to-code comparisons. The scenarios are based on the turbine trip 2 with additional system failures. The results presented here are for the most extreme scenario with both bypass valve failure and no scram. There are no reference results available, therefore the S5K results together with the results of other benchmark participants [9] are presented in this paper.

The results for the total power and the dome pressure are shown in Figure 7. The initial power peak and the initial pressure increase during the first 2 s is predicted consistently with the other benchmark participants. Compared to the average of other codes, S5K predicts the initial power peak higher and about 0.1 s earlier, however the deviations among the other codes were larger (the power delta change ranged from $7E9$ to $2E10$ W). S5K predicts larger pressure oscillations after a few seconds from the beginning of the transient, compared to the average of other codes. There are several differences in the modeling approach, one problem is that the benchmark cross sections used by the participants were created with CASMO-3, where the void coefficients differ significantly from the data used in S5K. In addition, the loss coefficients at the inlet and exit of the core were reversed in the NEA benchmark specification. In S5K, the data from the EPRI report are used.

Figure 7. Extreme scenario – bypass valve failure and no scram; S5K results and NEA benchmark participants results [9].

4. CONCLUSIONS

The Peach Bottom 2 Turbine Trip test 2 was modeled with the nodal transient code SIMULATE5-K. The power peak and the LPRM measurements are well-predicted by S5K. The calculated steam dome pressure is smaller than the measured values. One reason for this difference could be associated with the higher bypass flow predicted by S5K as compared to the measurements.

The results for the more extreme transient scenario, combining more system failures, show satisfactory agreement with the other benchmark participants in the prediction of the power peaks and the initial pressure rise.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Bahadir. “Development and Benchmarking of Transient Nodal Code SIMULATE5-K Neutron Kinetics Solver,” in *Proc. of PHYSOR2022*, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA (2022).
- [2] P. Mala, T. Bahadir, G. Grandi. “Verification of Nodal Transient Code SIMULATE5-K against the NEACRP Control Rod Ejection Accident Benchmark,” in *Proc. of ANFM2025*, Clearwater Beach, FL, USA (2025).

- [3] W. C. Dawn, G. Grandi, T. Bahadir. "Initial Validation of SIMULATE5-K and the CMS5 Reactor Modeling Suite with the SPERT-III Experiments," in *Proc. of PHYSOR2024*, San Francisco, CA, USA (2024).
- [4] G. Grandi. "Benchmark of SIMULATE5-K Against Frigg Loop Experiments," in *Proc. of ANFM2025*, Clearwater Beach, FL, USA (2025).
- [5] "Core Design and Operating Data for Cycles 1 and 2 of Peach Bottom 2." EPRI NP-563 (1978). URL <https://www.osti.gov/servlets/purl/6561294>
- [6] J. Solis, et al. "Boiling Water Reactor Turbine Trip (TT) Benchmark. Volume I: Final Specifications." NEA/NSC/DOC(2001)1, Rev. 1.
- [7] T. Bahadir and S.-O. Lindahl. "Studsvik's Next Generation Nodal Code SIMULATE5," in *Proc. of Advances in Nuclear Fuel Management IV*, Hilton Head Island, South Carolina, USA (2009).
- [8] L. A. Carmichael, R. O. Niemi. "Transient and Stability Tests at Peach Bottom Atomic Power Station Unit 2 at End of Cycle 2." EPRI NP-564 (1978).
- [9] B. Akdeniz, K. N. Ivanov, A. M. Olson. "Boiling Water Reactor Turbine Trip (TT) Benchmark. Volume IV: Summary Results of Exercise 3." NEA/NSC/DOC(2010)11.